

Matchmaking at professional innovation level

- There is no national overview platform about who is doing what and where, making it difficult for SMEs to identify partners outside their existing networks.
- Existing offers from the location promotion agencies tend to have a local/regional focus, based on one-on-one advance.
- There is a clear need of a robust platform at the Federal level that integrates existing offers and databases, potentially engaging AI, to allow partners to interact directly with each other.

Rethinking pathways for success

- Continuing education around the topic of innovation should be offered more, and to the top management of companies, to help sensitise them to the mindset of universities.
- Academic institutions and associations should provide better orientation towards appropriate knowledge sources, as well as relevant networks, to help institutionalize exchanges between disciplines.
- It is important to promote entrepreneurial thinking with long-term strategic planning.

Anchoring and living a culture of innovation

- Innovation requires a strong culture to be established and lived at all levels of a company. Freedom without time pressure, including the possibility of failure, must be made possible.
- Innovation funding bodies, associations, initiatives, and matchmakers play an important role in inspiring success stories and simplifying access to networks.
- Large consortia of industry and research partners along value chains are highly desirable but hardly feasible within Switzerland, collaboration abroad is thus urgently needed.

Innovation Strength Analysis 2024

Maintaining Switzerland's competitiveness relies on a highly innovative industrial sector. Despite challenges like a shrinking workforce and research limitations, a recent analysis by SATW and Swissmem shows that strategic investments are essential to fostering innovation and ensuring continued economic growth.

Read the full study here